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SCIENCE &
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Scientific Open Access Conference

MONEY LAUNDERING QUIETLY EXHAUSTS THE VERY HEART OF THE ECONOMY.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17837288>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 27th November 2025

Accepted: 28th November 2025

Online: 29th November 2025

KEYWORDS

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Money laundering is the process of re-processing proceeds derived from criminal activity with the aim of concealing their illicit origin. This process is of great importance because it allows an offender to use the proceeds of crime in a seemingly lawful manner while ensuring that their true source remains undisclosed.

The issue of money laundering is also addressed in the 1988 Vienna Convention of the United Nations (UN). Article 3.1 of the Convention defines money laundering as follows: “*The conversion or transfer of property, knowing that such property is derived from any offence, for the purpose of concealing or disguising the illicit origin of the property or of assisting any person who is involved in the commission of the offence to evade the legal consequences of his actions.*”¹

In addition to this, Articles 6 and 7 of the 2000 UNTOC Convention include norms related to combating money laundering, while Articles 12, 13, and 14 regulate the confiscation of proceeds of crime. Similarly, Articles 14, 23, and 24 of the 2003 UNCAC Convention contain measures aimed at countering money laundering, whereas Article 31 and Articles 51–59 in Chapter V establish procedures for freezing and confiscating assets derived from criminal activity.²

According to Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 660-II of 26 August 2004 “On Combating the Legalization of Proceeds from Criminal Activity, the Financing of Terrorism, and the Financing of the Proliferation of Weapons of Mass Destruction,” the basic concepts are defined as follows:

“**Proceeds from criminal activity**” are money or other property obtained as a result of committing a crime, as well as any benefit or profit derived from the use of such property, and likewise money or other property that has been wholly or partially transformed or converted into other property, or mixed with property obtained from lawful sources.

¹ URL: <https://www.unodc.org/unodc/en/money-laundering>

² “United Nations Convention Against Illicit Traffic in Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances”

“**Legalization of proceeds from criminal activity (money laundering)**” is an act constituting a socially dangerous offense punishable by law, which consists of giving a lawful appearance to money or other property obtained as a result of criminal activity by transferring, converting, or exchanging them, as well as concealing or disguising the true nature, source, location, disposition, movement, or ownership rights of such money or property, or concealing or disguising their true owner³ is considered.

Although the term “**money laundering**” officially emerged in the United States in the 20th century, in fact, this practice—i.e., giving a lawful appearance to assets and wealth obtained through illegal means in order to freely use them—has been employed since ancient times by those engaged in economic crimes⁴.

For example, after Al Capone — the head of the largest mafia organization in the United States in the 1930s — was arrested, the mafia’s accountant, Meyer Lansky (original surname Sukhomlynsky), who was of Jewish origin, deposited the proceeds from drug trafficking into anonymous bank accounts in Switzerland (which was relatively easy at that time). He then obtained various business loans from those same banks and subsequently repaid them using the “dirty” money stored in those accounts. Through this scheme, he achieved his main objective — effectively “legalizing” the illegally obtained funds⁵.

According to various sources, the roots of money laundering can be traced back to 2000 BCE. In this context, it is noted that “wealthy Chinese merchants laundered their incomes to circumvent government trade restrictions and invested them in other business ventures”⁶.

Similar methods were also used in ancient Rome and the Near East to evade taxes or conceal illicit income. During the Middle Ages, pirates attempted to legitimize their illegally acquired wealth by melting down stolen gold and selling it through lawful merchants or purchasing valuable goods.

The modern form of legalizing criminal proceeds began to emerge in the early 20th century in the United States. During the era of Prohibition, which prohibited the production and sale of alcoholic beverages, criminal gangs sought to conceal the substantial illegal profits they earned from the clandestine production and sale of alcohol.

In the 1970s and 1980s, drug trafficking in the United States expanded significantly, and narcotics cartels freely placed their criminal proceeds in domestic and foreign banks, later using them as apparently legitimate income.

One of the leaders of such criminal enterprises was the Colombian drug lord Pablo Emilio Escobar Gaviria (1949–1993), considered one of the world’s most notorious criminals. In the 1970s, he established the Medellín Cartel and began controlling cocaine trade directed to the United States, and by the 1980s, he controlled nearly 80% of the cocaine business. At

³ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 660-II of 26 August 2004 “On Combating the Legalization of Proceeds from Criminal Activity, the Financing of Terrorism, and the Financing of the Proliferation of Weapons of Mass Destruction” (*Legislative Information Database*, 21 April 2021, No. 03/21/683/0375)

⁴ URL: <https://isloimmoliyasi.uz/uz/7613-2/>

⁵ URL: <https://isloimmoliyasi.uz/uz/7613-2/>

⁶The History of Money Laundering: Know The Important Origin Of Money Laundering.
URL: <https://financialcrimeacademy.org/the-history-of-money-laundering-2/>

that time, his wealth exceeded USD 30 billion, making him one of the richest individuals in the world.

During the 1970s–1980s, money laundering became a global problem due to the proliferation of drug trafficking. In 1986, the United States enacted the **Money Laundering Control Act**, which is recognized as the first specific law addressing this issue.⁷

The primary reason for adopting this law was the need to combat the large volume of illicit proceeds generated from drug trafficking during the 1980s. Through this legislation, the United States sought to dismantle the financial foundations of criminal groups engaged in narcotics trafficking.

However, the term *money laundering* was officially used earlier—first in newspapers reporting on the Watergate scandal in 1973 and later in a court case in 1982.

Money laundering was defined in the **1988 United Nations Convention against Illicit Traffic in Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances (Vienna Convention)**. This convention required member states to criminalize the legalization of proceeds derived from drug trafficking within their national legislation. Subsequently, based on this Convention, the **40 international standards of the FATF** were adopted in 1990.

In 1989, the **Financial Action Task Force (FATF)** was established in response to the significant global economic harm caused by money laundering. FATF became the primary international body responsible for developing global standards to combat money laundering.

The September 11, 2001 terrorist attacks had a profound impact on anti-money laundering legislation. Following the attacks, the United States adopted the **Patriot Act**, which strengthened AML programs and imposed stricter oversight on foreign bank accounts. This law enhanced and expanded the provisions of the 1986 *Money Laundering Control Act* and improved information sharing between law enforcement agencies and financial institutions.

As U.S. efforts intensified, similar measures began to be implemented globally.

Today, money laundering is widely recognized as a process consisting of **three main stages**:

- **Placement** — introducing illicit funds into the financial system, typically by depositing cash in small amounts or integrating it into business operations.
- **Layering** — obscuring the origin of the funds through numerous complex transactions, including the use of offshore companies.

Integration — reintroducing the “cleaned” funds into the legitimate economy as lawful income.⁸ Purchasing real estate, art objects, and other valuable assets is also commonly used.

This model was proposed by Peter Reiman in the 1990s and remains a fundamental theoretical framework to this day.

As technology advances, money laundering methods are becoming increasingly complex. Examples include:

- Laundering via cryptocurrencies;
- Falsifying trade invoices;

⁷ History of Anti-Money Laundering Laws. URL: <https://www.fincen.gov/resources/history-anti-money-laundering-laws>.

⁸ URL: <https://oxfordre.com/criminology/display/10.1093/acrefore/9780190264079.001.0001/acrefore-9780190264079-e-708>

- Transferring large sums under the guise of charitable donations through various foundations, among others.

For instance, according to **Chainalysis data**, in 2023, approximately **\$24 billion** was laundered through cryptocurrencies such as **Bitcoin and Monero**.⁹

The essence of money laundering can be understood in both narrow and broad terms. In our view, in the narrow sense, it refers to the legalization of illegal funds by individuals or legal entities. In the broad sense, it can be defined as a socially dangerous act aimed at converting criminal capital into legal capital and supporting the long-term activities of individuals or groups who commit crimes.

Nowadays, such activities cause significant harm to economic stability. For example, they contribute to rising inflation, reduced tax revenues, and the distortion of competitive environments, which in turn negatively affects production.

Furthermore, money laundering leads to numerous social consequences. For instance, it contributes to the increase of criminal activity and reduces citizens' trust in the state. According to data provided by the World Bank in 2021, Mexican drug cartels laundered approximately **\$30 billion annually**, controlling about **10% of the national economy**.

Statistical data indicates that "...currently, more than **\$2 trillion** is legalized annually through money laundering."¹⁰

In our Republic, a number of measures are also being implemented to combat money laundering crimes. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 660-II of August 26, 2004, "On Combating the Legalization of Proceeds from Criminal Activity and the Financing of Terrorism," was revised and newly adopted on January 15, 2019, under the title "On Combating the Legalization of Proceeds from Criminal Activity, the Financing of Terrorism, and the Financing of the Proliferation of Weapons of Mass Destruction," thereby strengthening measures against such offenses.

In Uzbekistan, liability for committing such crimes is also established in Article 243 of the Criminal Code. According to this provision:
"Legalization of proceeds derived from criminal activity—meaning the transfer, conversion, or exchange of property (money or other assets) obtained as a result of criminal activity in order to give it a lawful appearance, as well as concealment or nondisclosure of the true nature, source, location, disposition, movement, ownership, or actual ownership rights to such funds or assets—is punishable by imprisonment for a term of five to ten years."

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⁹ Chainalysis. (2024). Crypto Crime Report.

¹⁰ So what exactly is money laundering? URL: <https://kyc-chain.com/the-history-of-money-laundering/>

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